

Influence of Astronomy on Ancient Architecture with a few South & Southeast Asian examples

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Abstract

Throughout history, architecture and astronomy have been deeply interconnected. As one of the oldest sciences, astronomy investigates celestial entities such as the sun, moon, planets, stars, and galaxies—essentially everything beyond Earth’s atmosphere. Architecture has significantly contributed to the advancement of astronomy, with various structures constructed for observational purposes since ancient times. Ancient observatories built by early civilizations and rulers exemplify this connection. Monuments like the Egyptian pyramids and Stonehenge in the UK were not merely architectural achievements but also served important astronomical functions. These structures have greatly improved our understanding of celestial phenomena. Since ancient times, astrology’s importance and its impact on daily life—from calendars to rituals—have been acknowledged. This study aims to explore the cultural and symbolic links between astronomy and architecture. By analysing few examples of architecture, this paper examines the design philosophies of their creators and the role of architectural typology in understanding these cultural and symbolic connections.

Key Words: astronomy, architecture, Sanchi stupa, Konark temple, Angkor Wat.

Introduction:

Since ancient times, architecture has been closely linked with astronomy. Astronomy, the study of outer space, is a natural science focused on exploring celestial bodies like the sun, moon, planets, stars, and galaxies—essentially everything beyond Earth's atmosphere. It is among the oldest scientific disciplines.

Long before the advent of clocks and calendars, people determined the time of day by observing the position of shadows on the ground and tracked the passage of months by the moon's phases in the night sky. They also identified patterns of stars, known as constellations, which were used to recognize seasonal changes—winter, spring, summer, or fall. Additionally, constellations helped ancient people record years and track the time elapsed since significant events.

A significant sign was provided to humanity when God positioned a star in the sky above Bethlehem to announce the arrival of the Savior. Wise men from a distant land saw this star and followed it to Bethlehem to find and honour Jesus. The star led them until it stopped above the place where the Child was. When they saw the star, they were overwhelmed with great joy. When they arrived at the house, they found the Child with Mary, His mother, and they fell to the ground in worship. They then unpacked their treasures and offered gifts of gold, frankincense, and myrrh. (Matthew 2:9-11)

Astronomy involves the study of stars and celestial phenomena, while architecture supports this field through specialized structures. To gain deeper insights into how architectural spaces contribute to astronomical research, an interdisciplinary approach that combines Astronomy, Archaeology, and Architecture can be illuminating. Numerous ancient monuments exhibit sophisticated spatial arrangements that link architectural design with astronomical observations. Analysing these architectural structures can reveal the underlying ideologies and conceptual changes in the design of spaces dedicated to astronomical studies (Sharma & Gola 2016).

Historically, astronomy has encompassed various fields such as celestial navigation, astrometry, observational astronomy, and calendar creation (Jain & Awasthi 2019). In architecture, astrology and climatology converge to form the *Vastu* philosophy (Dolan 2021).

In the Mediterranean region, astronomical knowledge influenced the design of structures intended to act as "mirrors" of the cosmos. These buildings integrated astronomical symbolism, miniature representations of the cosmos, and references to Earth, Heaven, and the movements of major celestial bodies (Asvadiya & Patel 2022).

Although some ancient constructions are known to have potentially served as astronomical observatories, they likely also had religious functions (Magli 2006). At that time, priests, who were well-versed in astronomy, used their knowledge of celestial movements for societal purposes. The oldest known structure oriented towards astronomical observations is the New Grange megalithic passage tomb, which dates back to 3200 BCE.

In southern England, there is an ancient stone monument known as Stonehenge. Many believe that it was used by ancient people to determine the arrival of spring by observing the sun's position relative to the large stones. This knowledge of seasonal changes helped them plan their planting and harvesting activities.

Various ancient civilizations constructed pyramids or pyramid-like structures. Significant examples include large pyramids in South America, Egypt, and China, as well as smaller pyramids in Greece, North America, the Canary Islands, and Indonesia.

The Giza Necropolis in Egypt provides another example. Egyptologists suggest that the smaller pyramids near the Great Pyramid of Khufu were used as burial sites for the Pharaoh's family. Some unexplored factors indicate that these pyramids may have served both as burial sites and as elements of an annual calendar, reflecting their intricate ground plan design. Architecture has been

employed to incorporate knowledge from various fields into symbolic three-dimensional forms (Asvadiya & Patel 2022).

In what is now Iran, the Radkan Tower stands as a testament to the intellectual prowess of the Persian Empire. Archaeologists believe that the renowned astronomer Nasir al-Din Tusi designed the tower to accurately predict seasonal and monthly changes (Hubbell 2024).

In ancient times, many megalithic structures were built around the world to align with the positions of star constellations. Although these structures were built by different cultures at various times, they exhibit certain structural and functional similarities that have puzzled modern archaeologists for centuries.

This paper will explore examples from South and Southeast Asian countries to further investigate architectural practices. Analysing the astronomical elements of ancient architecture offers valuable insights into the diverse aspects of our historical heritage.

Literature review

Šprajc *et al.* suggested that a thorough examination of building layouts in the Maya Lowlands reveals extensive and enduring design patterns that likely reference celestial alignments. Their findings offer new insights into the cosmic and calendrical significance of key structures at Chichén Itzá, one of the major sites studied, and prompt a reconsideration of previous interpretations (Šprajc & Sánchez Nava 2013).

Martinazzo *et al.* highlighted the challenges associated with processing and analysing large volumes of image data that emerged with the advent of photometric surveys in astronomy (Martinazzo, Espadoto, & Hirata 2020).

Asvadiya *et al.* explored the architectural concepts of observatory builders through various case studies and discussed the importance of architectural typology. They also examined how understanding cultural symbolism contributes to the study of these structures (Asvadiya & Patel 2022).

Discussion

The Great Sanchi Stupa, India

In examining the history of observational astronomy in India, the alignments found in ancient monuments hold significant value. The Buddhist monuments at Sanchi, especially the stupas, are among the oldest surviving architectural stone structures, dating back to the era of Emperor Ashoka in the third century BCE. Originally built to enshrine the relics of Buddha, the stupa evolved to symbolize Buddhist cosmology, meticulously oriented towards the four cardinal directions and incorporating numerical symbolism into its design (Volwashen 1969).

Marshall (1940) notes that the Great Stupa was initially constructed by Ashoka around 250 BCE as a hemispherical dome with a cylindrical brick base set in clay. The original structure had a diameter of 60 feet at the base, and it was topped with a *harmika* (crowning pinnacle) and one or more umbrellas (*chatravali*), all enclosed within a smaller square railing at the dome's summit. In addition to the stupa, Ashoka erected an edict pillar in 254 BCE, positioned about 50 feet from the railing.

Subsequently, around 150 BCE, the Sunga kings, likely Agnimitra, undertook significant expansions of the Great Stupa, nearly doubling its size. The expanded stupa was encased in masonry, with the dome (*anda*) increasing to over 120 feet in diameter and its height reaching approximately 54 feet.

Regarding the stupa's orientation, Marshall (1940) observes that “the entrance (South) did not face directly south but was offset by 15 degrees west of south. This deviation was likely due to the position of the Ashoka pillar, a fixture that could not be easily moved.”

However, the primary critique of Marshall's interpretation is that if the stupa's orientation was intentionally shifted by 15 degrees, there would have been no necessity to align other stupas (such as stupas 2 and 3) in the same manner. Yet, both stupas 2 and 3 are aligned precisely like stupa 1, suggesting that the Sunga rulers deliberately oriented stupa 1 by 15 degrees west. The reason for this intentional deviation remains unexplained.

The stupa is believed to symbolize Buddha, with the Great Stupa thought to contain relics of Lord Buddha (Marshall 1940). Consequently, its orientation might reflect significant events in Buddha's life. It is recorded that Buddha (Gautama) attained *nirvana* at Kushinagar on the full moon day of Vaisakha in 544 BCE, a day known as Buddha Purnima, which holds major religious significance for Buddhists. On this full moon day, the moonrise and sunset are separated by approximately 180 degrees and are observable on the eastern and western horizons.

One possibility is that the Sunga rulers oriented the stupa towards the directions of moonrise and sunset on Buddha Purnima. Given that the exact date of the stupa's construction is unknown and considering that Buddha Purnima could have occurred between April 28 and March 29 in 150 BCE due to variations in the lunar calendar, we calculated the directions of moonrise and sunset at Sanchi on Buddha Purnima day (as detailed in the Indian Astronomical Ephemeris on May 4, 1985), when the moon's declination was 14.07 degrees. This calculation aimed to determine if the stupa's orientation matched these celestial events.

Our analysis found that the stupa's east-west entrances align with the directions of moonrise (zenith distance = 90 degrees, azimuth = 105.35 degrees) and sunset (zenith distance = 85.9

degrees, azimuth = 74.3 degrees). This alignment supports the hypothesis that the 15-degree misalignment of the stupa may be explained by its orientation towards significant astronomical events on Buddha Purnima (Kameswara 1992:94).

Balustrades encircling the stupa

Regarding the balustrades, Volwashen (1969) notes that “the ends of the Swastikas, which form the approaches to the lower *pradakshina patha*, symbolize the sun’s trajectory. The practice of circumambulation is deeply linked with ancient solar cults, as evidenced by the procession starting in the east and following the sun’s path southwards and then westwards. The number of uprights is likely connected to the zodiac’s division into twelve parts and the solar journey across the horizon divided into twelve hour-angles,” thus adding an astronomical dimension to the structure.

The *harmika* balustrade features a square format with seven posts on each side, totalling 28 posts. The square shape represents permanence and immobility. This arrangement might symbolize the 28 "lunar mansions" (*nakshatras* or stellar groups) along the lunar path (Dikshit 1969:72).

It appears that there is a systematic approach to the arrangement of balustrades in the stupas of Sanchi. The outer balustrade symbolizes the lunar months and other moon-related phenomena. In contrast, the inner balustrade represents solar aspects or solar-lunar connections, such as the Metonic cycle or adjustments to align the lunar calendar with solar months. The innermost *harmika* balustrade, on the other hand, represents the *nakshatras*, which are farther away than both the moon and the sun (Kameswara 1992:97).

The Konark Sun temple

Konark is renowned for its magnificent Sun Temple, which is now in a state of ruin. The Konark Sun Temple, situated in Odisha, India, is known for its architectural splendour and astronomical significance. Built in the 13th century by King Narasimhadeva I of the Eastern Ganga Dynasty, the temple is commonly known as the 'Black Pagoda'. Intended to carry the sun god Surya, it was designed to look like a massive chariot with seven horses and 24 wheels.

The temple complex covers approximately 11 acres. Originally, the main temple stood 228 feet tall, while the *Jagamohana* (the assembly hall) was 150 feet high. Today, the main temple is destroyed, and the *Jagamohana* is partially in ruins. The temple's tower and porch were once visible from the sea for a considerable distance, serving as a navigational landmark for mariners.

Additionally, the temple's walls are adorned with intricate carvings featuring astronomical motifs, including celestial deities, zodiac signs, and planetary positions. These carvings not only serve as decorative elements but also symbolize the cosmic order and the cyclical nature of time.

Placement of the monuments with relation to solar path

The astronomical alignment of the Konark Sun Temple not only displays the architectural brilliance of ancient India but also reflects the profound spiritual and scientific knowledge of its creators. The temple continues to captivate visitors and scholars, highlighting the enduring connection between human civilization and the cosmos.

The builders possessed an extensive understanding of culture, astronomy, and architecture. Konark's artisans designed the Sun Temple, *Jagamohana*, *Nata Mandira*, and Eastern Gate with such precision that the first rays of the sun would fall on the head of the sun god seated on the throne of the Sun Temple, passing through the doors of all the structures. The doors are aligned according to the sun's position in various seasons. The *Nata Mandira* is specifically constructed so that sunlight streams through its pillars to illuminate the sun god's idol. The pillars are carefully positioned to ensure that sunlight passes unobstructed during both *Uttarayana* (the northern movement of the sun) and *Dakshinayana* (the southern movement of the sun).

Play of light and shadow – the accuracy of the sundial of Konark

During the construction of the Sun Temple, careful attention was given to the sun path diagram to ensure the temple's precise orientation.

The temple features 24 intricately carved wheels. Each wheel's axles extend approximately one foot from the surface. Of these 24 wheels, 6 are located on either side of the main temple, 4 are positioned on each side of the *Jagamohana*, and 2 are placed on each side of the steps at the eastern front. Twelve of these wheels are particularly large, with a diameter of 2.92 meters. Fergusson (1910) lauds the temple's design, noting that, the interplay of light and shadow from its striking and diverse projections creates a dazzling and vibrant effect. Just as the sun tracks time, the temple's symbolism reflects this theme.

Praharaj notes that,

“The vertical sundial has been designed for the particular latitude of Konark. The shadows made by these sundials give exact time of the day. The sundial built in the thirteenth century is accurate. The sundial has 8 major spokes that divide 24 hours into 8 equal parts, which means that the time between two major spokes is 3 hours. There are 8 minor spokes as well. Each minor spoke runs exactly in the middle of 2 major spokes. This means that the minor spoke divides the 3 hours in half, so the time between a major spoke and a minor spoke is an hour and half or 90 minutes. At the edge of the wheel, there are 30 beads between a major and minor spoke. So the 90 minutes are further divided by 30 beads. This means that each bead carries a value of 3 minutes. The beads are large enough to observe the shadow falls on the bead. This way, one can calculate time accurately to the minute.

“The sundial shows time in an anti-clockwise fashion. From the top, the major spoke stands for midnight, 3 AM and 6 AM and so on. This wheel is a unique masterpiece in the world, designed by the astronomers and sculptors” (Praharaj 2015, 16-19).

Similarly, the three grand stupas of Anuradhapura and Angkor Wat in Cambodia appear to be aligned with specific star constellations.

For centuries, Sri Lankans viewed these ancient stupas primarily as sacred sites enshrining the remains of Lord Buddha and the arhants, or enlightened ones.

The three major stupas of Anuradhapura—Mirisavatiya, Ruvanweliya, and Jetavanaya—are thought to align with the three stars in the constellation Orion: Rigel, Al Nitak, and Bellatrix. Built between 161 BCE and 331 CE, the triangular layout of these stupas closely mirrors the triangular pattern of these Orion stars, creating a symbolic connection between heaven and earth.

These celestial alignments and advanced construction techniques have fascinated researchers and archaeologists for generations. Despite extensive study, the full secrets of these monumental structures remain elusive.

Recent research in Sri Lanka suggests that the Ruwanweliseya of Anuradhapura might have functioned as a massive energy storage device, potentially interacting with the skies above. According to a multi-disciplinary investigation led by architect Shereen Amendra, the Ruwanweliseya, also known as the Mahathupa, was designed as a large capacitor capable of exchanging electrical charges with the heavens.

The Mahavamsa, the great chronicle of Sri Lanka, records that the site for the Mahathupa was chosen by Lord Buddha himself, and the structural design was planned by the arhants of the Maha Vihara. The stupa, which houses numerous relics of Lord Buddha, was constructed with precious metals such as silver and gold and valuable stones, all known for their excellent electrical conductivity.

Angkor Wat in Cambodia, the largest Hindu temple complex and the largest religious monument in the world, was built in the 12th century and is believed to represent the constellation Draco.

Draco, a constellation in the far northern sky, is Latin for "dragon." It was one of the 48 constellations listed by the 2nd-century Greek astronomer Ptolemy and remains one of the 88 modern constellations today. Draco is notable for its location around the north celestial pole, making it circumpolar from northern latitudes—it never sets and is visible year-round.

Angkor Wat combines the traditional temple mountain design, characteristic of the empire's state temples, with later concentric gallery plans rooted in Hindu religious beliefs. Extensive research in the 1970s (Stencel *et al.* 1976) and subsequent updates by Eleanor Mannikka have revealed that Angkor Wat functioned as a practical observatory. The temple's design aligns with solar events, such as the equinoxes and solstices, with the western entrance oriented to these astronomical phenomena. Sightlines within the temple also track seasonal risings of the sun and moon.

The temple's orientation and specific features reflect its celestial significance. For instance, the main tower aligns with the morning sun on the spring equinox (www.art-and-archaeology.com). Angkor Wat symbolizes Mount Meru, the sacred mountain in Hindu mythology, with its central quincunx of towers representing the mountain's five peaks, and its surrounding walls and moat symbolizing the mountain ranges and ocean encircling it (Freeman & Jacques 1999). Access to the upper areas of the temple was increasingly restricted, with the laity permitted only to the lowest level (Glaize 1944).

The remarkable sophistication of Angkor Wat's geometry reveals the builders' intention to forge a profound connection with the cosmos through what they considered sacred numerology. Far from being a display of a ruler's vanity, Angkor Wat was designed as a tool to help people establish a tangible link with the divine. Its measurements are interlinked based on ancient astrological observations, leading some to propose that Angkor Wat might function as an advanced calendar or cosmic clock.

According to scholar, historian, and mathematician Shubash Kak (2001), Angkor Wat comprises at least three astronomical and architectural units that together form a vast cosmic diagram:

1. The Central Sanctuary: Representing Mount Meru, this symbolizes the celestial North Pole, the Earth's axis, and the spring equinox.
2. The Outer Corridors and Concentric Galleries: These symbolize the ecliptic, Earth's and planetary orbits, lunar cycles, constellations, and solar and lunar years.
3. The Four Axes of the Temples: Representing cosmic ages and cycles of time.

Notably, just a hundred meters from Angkor Wat stands Phnom Bakheng, a five-tiered pyramid 76 meters wide at its base, topped by four towers and a central sanctuary. This structure includes 104 smaller towers on the lower terraces, which total 108 when including the four top towers. This arrangement reflects the 27 days of a lunar month, while the lateral towers and central sanctuary mark the Sun's position during the solstices and equinoxes. The upper five terraces each have 12 towers, corresponding to the 12 years of the Jupiter cycle, which forms the basis of the Khmer sacred calendar. Consequently, Phnom Bakheng has been described as a stone-based astronomical calendar. Similarly, other notable Angkor monuments, such as the Bayon with its 54 towers and the Pre Rup with its 27 towers, also embody significant astronomical and calendrical symbolism.

Conclusion

This research paper states that since the old-time 1000 years ago people are intelligent and they know about astrology and how to use architecture in astronomy study. When that time technology is not available compared to today's modern time. They know about how important architecture calculation and building are important parts of study. They know the relation between Astrology and Architecture. Use as an old schedule by utilizing space science observatory a schedule to characterize the consistencies of the sun, moon, stars, and heavenly bodies. Utilizing an architecture, they had the option to track down Directions with accuracy, cosmic perception,

noticing the peculiarities to the seasons, estimating the lengths of the sun's shadow, noticing the course of dawn to decide the seasons and orientated to dusk and so forth.

The interplay between astronomy and architecture in ancient civilizations reveals a profound understanding of celestial phenomena and their integration into the built environment. This synergy not only shows the sophistication of ancient societies but also highlights their ability to merge scientific knowledge with artistic expression. The architectural marvels created by these civilizations reflect their deep reverence for the cosmos and their desire to align their structures with celestial events.

In South and Southeast Asia, this influence is particularly evident. For example, the ancient Sun Temple at Konark in India demonstrates how intricate architectural design was employed to represent celestial cycles; the Great Stupa of Sanchi with its outer balustrades symbolizing lunar months and its central *harmika* aligning with the *nakshatras*. Similarly, the temples of Angkor Wat in Cambodia illustrate how astronomical alignment was integral to their design, with the complex mirroring the constellation Draco and serving as an advanced observatory for tracking solar and lunar events. In Sri Lanka, the stupas of Anuradhapura, such as the Ruwanweliseya, reflect a deep astronomical awareness. Their construction aligns with key celestial features, revealing the builders' sophisticated understanding of cosmic cycles and their use of architectural forms to reflect these phenomena. The pyramidal structure of Phnom Bakheng further exemplifies this integration, functioning as a stone-based calendar and symbolizing lunar and solar cycles.

These examples from South and Southeast Asia show a universal theme: ancient architects and astronomers harnessed their knowledge of celestial bodies to influence their architectural creations, crafting structures that were both practical and symbolic. This integration of astronomy and architecture displays the technical skill of ancient builders as well as their desire to connect with the divine and grasp their place in the universe. Such achievements remain a source of inspiration and fascination, highlighting the enduring significance of celestial influences in

architectural design. This thematic study aimed to explore the distinctiveness and creativity of these ancient practices, thereby enhancing the global appreciation of astronomical sites.

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